

1 **Neurod specifies identity in the CNS.**

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7 Neurod factors establish identity in the CNS by controlling lineage specification at the transcriptional level
8 and by controlling expression of genes with tissue-restricted expression in the CNS. We identified Neurod
9 regulated gene products and the broader Neurod program using a discovery approach by querying
10 transcriptome-wide across a multitude of cellular settings in human cells and tissues for genes regulated
11 by Neurod1, Neurod2, Neurod4 and Neurod6. Neurod controlled the expression of a group of nuclear
12 factors including *BHLHE22*, *ZCCHC12*, *SOHLH1*, and the brain T-box Tbr1, as well as genes functioning
13 in switching in lineage commitment in the central nervous system including Dlx1, Dlx2 and Bcl11a. One
14 group of genes included the Neurexin (NRXN), Neuroexophilin (NXPH), and Neurensin (NRSN) families.
15 Cerebellin-2 and cerebellin-4 were Neurod-regulated gene products. CHD3 and CHD5 defined epigenetic
16 control of neurogenesis regulated by the Neurod program. Cell adhesion important for neurogenesis and
17 for function in the vertebrate CNS including DSCAM and L1CAM as well as axon guidance factors
18 ROBO2 and SLIT1, and the SLITRK receptor genes SLITRK1-4 were key Neurod regulated genes.
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